

CANDIDIASIS INFECTIONS, CURRENT CHALLENGES, PROGRESS IN PREVENTION AND TREATMENT

Zainab Khaled Masalwa

Al-Mustansiriya University, College of Science, Department of Life Sciences

Noor AL Huda Ali Hamza

University of Babylon College of Sciences, Biology Department

Hadeer Jamal Moneam

Al Farabi University College of Sciences, Biology Department

Zainab Mahdi Khalif

University of Mosul, College of Science, Department of Life Sciences/Microbiology

Abstract: -

Candida, yeast like fungus, is common organism present in the reproductive and gastrointestinal mucosa and can be isolated from the oral cavity and hence up 80% of healthy population is found to be prone to the most common fungal infection such as candidiasis.

Candida species produce infection that range from non-life threatening mucocutaneous illnesses to invasive conditions. Candida albicans and other species such Candida glabrata, Candida krusei and etc. represents an important source of systemic infection worldwide. These organisms are the most common cause of superficial vaginal or mucosal oral infections and may also under propitious conditions, enter the bloodstream leading to deep tissue infection.

The etiological and biochemical characteristic of Candida albicans make it biologically microbe, it's pathological potential make it medically important microorganism

Oral Candidiasis is on opportunistic infection of the oral cavity. It's common and under diagnosed among elderly, particularly in this wear dentures. Oral Candidiasis caused by an overgrowth or infection of oral cavity by yeast like fungus, candida. These infections ranging from oral thrush and vaginitis to deep systemic. Systemic infections are commonly referred to as Candidemia and one of prominent co infection in immune compromised patients such those suffering from cancer, HIV etc. with use of powerful antibiotics and immune suppressive therapies during organ transplant or anti leukemia therapies.

Therefore, to prevent and treat oral candidiasis(fungi), you must adhere to oral hygiene, stay away from Fitted dentures and treat hypo-salivation etc. There is large variety of medication like Topical antifungal Therapy include Nystatin, widely used ,liquid creams and pastilles , Clotrimazole is an alternative to nystatin that us especially useful in angular cheilitis and Miconazole, antifungal can be used both topically and systemically , while Systemic anti-fungal Therapy is preferred in severely immune compromised patients, and treatment usually by a physician like Fluconazole, the preferred agent, observed in

gastrointestinal tract and taken orally with good effect . Diagnosis of oral Candidiasis can be done by microscopic examination and /or biopsy also fungal culture.

The review provides for an overview on, candida, predisposing factors, preventing, diagnoses and treatment of oral Candidiasis, highlighting alternative approaches for Candidiasis treatment.

Introduction

Candida, yeast like fungus, is a common organism present in the reproductive and gastrointestinal mucosa and can be isolated from the oral cavity and hence up to 80% of the healthy population is found to be prone to the most common fungal infections such as candidiasis. Candida species produce infections that range from non-life threatening mucocutaneous illnesses to invasive conditions which may involve severe infection to destruction of vital organs (Walsh and Dixon 1996; Eckert *et al.* 2012).

Candida albicans and other species including *Candida glabrata*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida tropicalis*, etc. represent an important source of systemic infections worldwide. These organisms are the most common cause of superficial vaginal or mucosal oral infections and may also, under propitious conditions, enter the bloodstream leading to deep-tissue infections (Conti *et al.* 2014).

Also, *Candida albicans* is a member of the human microflora as a diploid polymorphic yeast of mucosal surfaces and is commonly found in the human gastrointestinal (GI), respiratory, and genitourinary tracts. It is generally a harmless commensal fungus that can turn into an opportunistic organism in immunocompromised or immunologically deficient individuals with a variety of host cells, (Kashem *et al.* 2015). An abnormal growth in *Candida albicans* due to environmental imbalance like reduction of pH may result in candidiasis. (Pfaller and Tenover 2007) As a commensal pathogen, *Candida* can adapt to hosts' environmental changes very quickly, even when nutrients bioavailability is restricted (Miramon and Lorenz 2017). Historically, *Candida albicans* is known to us since 400 BC when the renowned Greek physician, Hippocrates, identified a microbial infection and he named it-as "thrush," which is caused by this pathogen (Anderson and Odds., 1985).

However, *Candida albicans* it was not studying like any other model organism till late twentieth Century and early studies were mainly confined to the identification of *Candida albicans* strain (Gordon. 1958)(Taschdjian, *et al.*, 1960)

The 1970 and 1980 some *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* laboratories started working on candida and in the 1990, large number of yeast laboratories switched to study aspect of *C. albicans* resulting in the initiation of genome sequencing of this pathogen in 1996.

The completion and availability of genome sequence of *C. albicans* in 2004 made possible to initiate rigorous research activities and expanded our knowledge of this important pathogen (Jones *et al.*, 2004).

Candida now cause approximately 7% of all nosocomial infection The etiological and biochemical characteristic of *Candida albicans* make it unique biologically microbe, its pathological potential make it a medically important microorganism *C. albicans* causing candidiasis can be isolated from gastrointestinal tracks of a wide variety of birds and mammal (winner and Hurley 1964; Emmons *et al.* 1977).

This yeast persists as a minor and sometimes major member of the alimentary tract microbial flora for life Normally balance between the host and potential parasite ,but when this balance is distributed by internal or external factors, the yeast multiply and it's millions of cell invade and destroy vital tissue of the host (Ajello, 1977).

Oral Candidiasis or thrush is fungal infection (presence of parasitic infection in or any part of body ,example mycoses) caused by any species from genera candida which *C. albicans* common causative species .The

infection referred to as candidiasis, moniliasis and also called yeast infection. This infection ranging from oral thrush and vaginitis to deep systemic which are mostly life threatening. Systemic infection are commonly referred to as candidemia and one of prominent coinfection in immuno-compromised patients such as those suffering from cancer, HIV etc. as well patients in non-trauma emergency surgery, with use of powerful antibiotics and immune-suppressive therapies during organ transplant or antileukemia therapies (Greenspan and John, 1996; wang, *et al.*, 2013).

The most important risk factors for candida infections are anti biotic therapy followed by central venous access, surgical procedures parenteral nutrition, urinary catheters as well some disease such as solid cancer, cardiac disease, trauma, neurological disease gastrointestinal disease pulmonary disease, vascular disease, HIV, genetic disease, renal disease, liver and pancreatic disease etc. (scanela, *et al.*, 2018)

In immunocompromised individual *C. albicans* induces systemic infection (Ballou, *et al.*, 2016).

And may turn from commensal infection of mouth, throat and reproductive tract to systemic candidiasis affecting the circulatory system, bone, brain (Kim and Sudbery, 2011).

In allergic individuals the chronic exposures to candida act as aggressive factor and lead production specific immunoglobulin E (IgE) against candida antigens (Savolainen, *et al.*, 1993).

Medically Important Candida Species:

Of the around 150 Candida species, that have been identified, more than 17 can cause invasive candidiasis (Pfaller and Diekema, 2004), approximately 90% of infections can be attributed to only 4 species: *C. albicans*, *C. glabrata*, *C.*

parapsilosis and *C. tropicalis* (Pfaller and Diekema, 2007). The importance of these species varies geographically but *C. albicans* is by far the most common cause of invasive candidiasis worldwide (Pfaller and Diekema, 2007). All Candida species are ascomycetes belonging to the group of hemi ascomycetes but the genus Candida is quite diverse. Most clinically relevant species including *C. albicans*, *C. parapsilosis* and *C. tropicalis* are members of the CTG clade, a group of fungi that uses CTG to encode serine rather than leucine (Santos and Tuite. 1995).

C. glabrata is much more closely related to the baker's yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. (Dujon, *et al.*, 2004).

As a consequence, *C. albicans* and *C. glabrata* differ in many aspects of their genetics, cell biology and biochemistry (Kaur, *et al.*, 2005) Unlike other clinically relevant Candida spp, *C. glabrata* is for example not diploid but an obligate haploid.

Furthermore *C. glabrata* does not exhibit polymorphism

Types of candida Diseases Include:

- 1-Candida infection in mouth, throat and esophagus (Oral candidiasis).
- 2-Vaginal candidiasis.
- 3-invasive candidiasis.
- 4-Nail candidiasis.
- 5-Anal candidiasis.
- 6-Urinary yeast infection.
- 7-Muco cutaneous candidiasis.
- 8-Intra abdominal candidiasis

Also, others Candidemia, Endocarditis, Meningitis, Endophthalmitis and Neutropenia (key risk factor)

Oral Candidiasis

is an opportunistic infection of the oral cavity. It's common and under diagnosed among the elderly, particularly in this wear dentures and in many cases is avoidable with good mouth care regimen. It can also mark of systemic disease, such as diabetes mellitus and is a common problem among the immunocompromised patient. Oral Candidiasis is caused by an overgrowth or infection of oral cavity by yeast like fungus, candida (Epstein, 1990: Guida, 1988).

More than 20 species of Candida, Candida albicans are the most common and important causative agent of oral Candidiasis (Premanathan *et al.*, 2011).

The conditions that contribute in the development of the infection include broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, xerostomia, immune dysfunction, or the presence of removable prosthesis or denture. Advances in medical management as antineoplastic chemotherapy, organ transplantation, hemodialysis, parenteral nutrition, and central venous catheters also contribute to fungal invasion and colonization (Mikulska, *et al.*, 2012). The incidence of candidiasis in the oral cavity with predominant C. albicans isolation has been reported to be 4565% in children (Lucas, 1993), 30- 45% of healthy adults (Arendorf and Walker. 1980), 90% in patients with acute leukemia undergoing chemotherapy (Dupont. 1992) and 95% of patients with HIV infection (Fraser. 1992).

Oral Candidiasis (Thrush)

The most common predisposing factors

Thrush (oral Candidiasis) is common fungal infection among HIV positive pediatric populations. In addition to immune systems defects in children, anemia, antiretroviral drugs, broad spectrum antibiotics, genetic, hospitalization, head and neck radiotherapy, diabetes, and malnutrition are frequent predisposing factors may lead to severe oral Candidiasis. Also, persistent childhood thrush is considered as a multi factorial fungal infection in which, pediatric individuals experience enormous morbidities with low level quality life. Also, the progression of HIV increases the severity of persistent thrush which may lead to mortality (Akpan and Morgan. 2002: Patton, *et al.*, 1999)

Extensive oral and oropharyngeal candidiasis are clear indicators for progressive status of HIV in patients with AIDS. (Cannon, *et al.*, 1995).

It's important to know that, the high colonization of *Candida* in oral cavity of children supports the phenomenon of dental decay (Signoretto, *et al.*, 2009).

Classification and TYPES

Oral candidiasis can be divided into many different types by its clinical appearance in the mouth, and sometimes by its predisposing factors as following:

1-Pseudomembranous Candidiasis

This form of candidiasis classically presents as acute infection, though the term chronic pseudomembranous candidiasis has been used to denote chronic recurrence cases. It is commonly seen in extremes of age, immune-compromised patients especially in AIDS, diabetics, patient's on corticosteroids, prolonged broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy, hematological, and other malignancies (Patil, *et al.*, 2015). They commonly occur as adherent white plaques resembling curdled milk or cottage cheese on the surface of the labial and buccal mucosa, hard and soft palates, tongue, periodontal tissues, and oropharynx. The membrane can be scrapped off with a swab to expose the underlying erythematous mucosa. It is often easily diagnosed and is one of the commonest forms of oropharyngeal candidiasis accounting for almost a third. (Silverman, *et al.*, 1984) The symptoms of the acute form are rather mild and the patients may complain only of slight tingling sensation or foul taste, whereas, the chronic forms may involve the esophageal mucosa leading to dysphagia and chest pains. Few lesions mimicking pseudomembranous candidiasis could be white coated tongue, thermal and chemical burn, leukoplakia, secondary syphilis and diphtheria (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013).

Pseudo membranous candidiasis.

Acute pseudo membranous.

2-Acute Erythematous (atrophic) Candidiasis

Atrophic or erythematous candidiasis is relatively rare and manifests as both acute and chronic forms (Ashman and Farah, 2005) Previously known as 'antibiotic sore mouth,' due to its association with prolonged use of broad-spectrum antibiotics

(Farah, *et al.*, 2010). Erythematous candidiasis appears as a red, more or less circumscribed lesion in the hard palate (Coronado and Jimenez *et al.*, 2013), can persist chronically and is usually asymptomatic (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013). A burning or itching sensation can occur (Giannini and Shetty, 2011) A bright red tongue can occur, and the differential diagnosis in these cases is low serum B12, folate and iron (McCullough and Savage, 2005).

3-Chronic Erythematous (atrophic) Candidiasis.

The chronic form is usually seen in HIV patients involving the dorsum of the tongue and the palate and occasionally the buccal mucosa. Patients who wear dentures continuously day and night are most commonly affected by the infection. This form of atrophic candidiasis is also termed as 'Denture sore mouth. The disease is characterized by formation of asymptomatic erythema and inflammation of entire denture bearing mucosa of the palate

Erythematous candidiasis

4-Hyper plastic Candidiasis.

Hyper-plastic candidiasis is the least common form of oral candidiasis, but its malignant potential makes it an important one (Akpan and Morgan, 2002). It is also called candidal leukoplakia, and like ordinary leukoplakia, it appears as white lesions that cannot be rubbed off (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009). Its appearance varies greatly, from small, translucent, slightly raised lesions, to large, plaque-like areas that feel hard and rough on palpation (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009), It is most commonly found on the buccal mucosa and is associated with smoking (Akpan and Morgan,2002).

Though it cannot be rubbed off, it can be separated from leukoplakia by microbiological tests, attempting treatment with anti-fungal medicine, or by taking a biopsy for histological examination (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009). In this form of the infection the *Candida* hyphae are not only found at epithelial surface level but also invade deeper levels where epithelial dysplasia can be observed, with the associated risk of malignancy (Sitheequ and Samaranayake, 2003).

Hyper plastic candidiasis at right lateral border of tough

5-Angular cheilitis.

Angular cheilitis is an inflammation of one, or more commonly both of the corners of the mouth. Initially, the corners of the mouth develop a gray-white thickening and adjacent erythema (redness). Later, the usual appearance is a roughly triangular area of erythema, edema (swelling) and maceration at either corner of the mouth (Scully and Crispian., 2008).

Angular cheilitis can occur spontaneously but more often develops in those who wear oral dentures and appliances, those who are required to wear masks as part of their occupation, and in some small children, particularly those who slobber and use pacifiers (Lamey and Lewis, 1989).

Typically, the lesions give symptoms of pain, pruritus (itching) or burning or a raw feeling in the later stage (Scully and Crispian,

2008).

Bilateral of Angular cheilitis

Angular cheilitis often represents an opportunistic infection of fungi and/or bacteria, with multiple local and systemic predisposing factors involved in the initiation and persistence of the lesion (Tyldesley, *et al.*, 2003).

6-Denture related Stomatitis.

Denture-related stomatitis refers to an inflammatory state of the denture bearing mucosa, characterized by chronic erythema and edema of part or all the mucosa beneath maxillary dentures (Dos Santos, *et al.*, 2009). It is also the most commonly encountered mucosal lesion with removable prostheses, and affects one in every three complete denture wearers (Emami, *et al.*, 2014). Denture stomatitis is also known as denture sore mouth, denture-induced stomatitis, and chronic atrophic candidiasis.

Although, etiology of denture stomatitis is considered multifactorial, denture plaque, trauma, candida albicans, allergy, adverse systemic conditions, surface texture and permeability of the denture base and lining materials are regarded as some of the major factors associated with the condition. In majority of the cases, elimination of denture faults, control of denture plaque and discontinuing the wearing of denture are sufficient (Arendorf and Walker. 1987).

Denture stomatitis has been classified into three subtypes depending on the severity of the lesion as types I, II and III. Type I is the localized simple form with inflammation or pinpoint hyperemia. Type II is a more diffuse erythematous form involving a part or the entire denture-covered mucosa. Type III presents as granular or papillary form involving the central part of the hard palate and alveolar ridge (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009).

7-Median Rhomboid Glossitis.

Median rhomboid glossitis is a diamond shaped, elevated, inflammatory lesion of the tongue, covered by smooth red mucosa. It is situated anterior to the circumvallate papillae, at about the junction of the anterior two-third and posterior one-third of the tongue (Cherrick, 1988). It predominantly affects males (Rogers, 2004) while few studies showed female preponderance (Avcu and Kanli, 2003). The most common clinical presentation of the disease is an erythematous or white- erythematous area on the dorsal median surface of the tongue, immediately prior to Region V of the circumvallate papilla (terminal gingiva). The erythematous region of the mucosa can be flat or raised. It is normally well circumscribed, with a rhomboid shape, and smooth. A nodular component is occasionally found, or the organ can be lobulated. The texture may be similar to the subjacent or firm part of the tongue, and its surface is relatively soft (Holmstrup and Besserman, 1983). In some patients with median rhomboid glossitis, oral Candidiasis may be seen in other sites such as the oral commissures and hard palate. Palatal "kissing lesion" usually results from direct inoculation that occurs when the dorsal tongue makes contact with the hard palate during deglutition. This presentation of erythematous candidiasis has been referred to as chronic multifocal candidiasis. (Neville, 2009).

Median rhomboid glossitis

8-linear gingival erythema.

Linear gingival erythema (LGE), which was formally referred as HIV-gingivitis, is the most common form of HIV- associated periodontal disease in HIV-infected population. It is considered resistant to conventional plaque-removal therapies, being considered, nowadays, a lesion of fungal etiology. It is characterized by a fired, linear band 2 to 3 mm wide on the marginal gingival accompanied by petechiae-like or diffuse red lesions on the attached gingival and oral mucosa, and may be accompanied by bleeding. The prevalence of this lesion varies widely in different studies, ranging from 0 to 48% probably because in many of them, LGE was misdiagnosed as gingivitis (Maristela Barbosa Portela, 2012). This fungus *saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *candida dubliniensis*, and opportunistic bacteria are thought to be the pathogens associated with this type of lesion. (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2000).

Linear gingival erythema

9-Aspergillosis.

Aspergillus fumigatus is the species most often implicated in human diseases. (Iatta, *et al.*, 2009). Aspergillosis is reportedly the second most common opportunistic fungal infection after candidiasis (Neville, *et al.*, 2009).

The fungus either invades blood vessels, causing thrombosis and infarction of surrounding tissue or invades the sinuses, progressively causing palatal and tongue lesion. (Torre-Cisneros, *et al.*, 1993). Oral aspergillosis is predominantly seen in immunocompromised individuals. Marginal gingiva and the gingival sulcus have been cited as the portal of entry of the spores (Neville, *et al.*, 2009) Painful gingival ulcerations and mucosal soft tissue swellings with gray or violaceous hue have been reported. This can advance to extensive necrosis and present clinically as a yellow or black ulcer with facial swelling (Shannon, *et al.*, 1990).

Aspergillosis Ulcer

10- Geotrichosis.

This is caused by the fungus *Geotrichum candidum* which has been isolated from the skin, sputum and feces of humans. It is carried in the alimentary tract of some individuals and can sometimes cause opportunistic infection (Samaranayake, *et al.* 2009).

The fungus infects the bronchi, lung, mouth and intestine. The oral lesions of geotrichosis are similar clinically to pseudomembranous candidiasis and differentiation can be done only by histopathological examination and culture of the organism. (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009).

Pseudo membranous Geotrichosis

Diagnostic tests.

Diagnosis of oral candidiasis relies largely on recognition of its physical appearance. However, tests should be made to confirm the diagnosis and determine susceptibility to anti fungals. This can be done using a microscope to see the fungal cells in a sample, or macroscopically with a fungal culture (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013).

Smear Staining.

For a microscopic test, a smear of the lesion is made. The smear can be stained in a number of different ways, and fixed to glass microscope slide with alcohol, or by simply air drying, before viewing under a microscope (Farah, *et al.*, 2010). A potassium hydroxide (KOH) solution can also be used, with gentle heating, which causes the epithelial cells from the mucosa to dissolve, leaving a clearer view of the fungal cells (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013).

While the mucosa should be swabbed, an adjacent nonrenewing surface will often carry a lot of extra organisms (Rautemaa and Ramage, 2011).

Biopsy.

In cases of hyperplastic candidiasis, or rather, in cases where it is suspected, a biopsy should be made along with the smear stain (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013). The mucosal tissue sample is placed in 10% formalin, before further processing, embedding in paraffin, and cutting (Giannini and Shetty, 2011). section is placed on a glass microscope slide and stained (for example PAS), and can be examined under a microscope (Giannini and Shetty, 2011).

Fungal Culture.

Fungal cultures can be cultured on Sabouraud dextrose agar (SDA) representing a common selective fungal growth medium (Farah, *et al.*, 2010). White colonies appear and indicate a positive culture result, but it does not necessarily indicate infection (Giannini and Shetty. 2011).

The cultures can be analyzed further for identification of the species and for testing of anti-fungal susceptibility (Farah, *et al.*, 2010). To determine sensitivity, or resistance, to an anti-fungal medication, fungal cultures with an Epsilonometer test, or E-test can be used (Sims, *et al.*, 2006).

An agar with chromogenic substrate can be used with mixedspecies samples, as the different species and their enzymes will react differently, their colonies will have various colors (Giannini and Shetty, 2011).

Manage and Treat of oral Candidiasis

Identifying the cause of infection for each individual patient is the first step in treating and oral candidiasis. Correcting the risks can be simple or challenging, depending on their severity. In many cases it becomes

necessary to involve the patient's physician, if the underlying condition is not so severe that they are involved from the start.

Oral hygiene.

In cases such as denture stomatitis, instructing the patient in proper oral hygiene is important (Rautemaa and Ramage, 2011). the patient is incapable of managing their own oral hygiene, their care takers must be instructed to do it for them. The initial treatment should include treating both the mouth and the denture with anti-fungal creams or ointments, and later the denture can be cleaned using soap or chlorhexidine (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013).

ILL Fitted dentures. ill-fitted dentures can be a contributing cause of denture stomatitis (Olsen and Orale infeksjoner, 2010). In addition to improving oral hygiene, regular relining of the denture is recommended for prophylaxis and treatment of denture stomatitis (Marin Zuluaga, *et al.*, 2011). Tissue conditioning is a temporary form of relining dentures, which provides the denture with a soft, cushioning base, allowing the mucosa to heal and normalize in shape (Marin Zuluaga, *et al.*, 2011).

Hypo-salivation.

Treating hypo salivation is a part of treating fungal infection, and strategies include frequent hydration and saliva substitutes. Pilocarpine and cevimeline can be prescribed as they increase salivary flow (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013).

Immunosuppression.

The most difficult patient to treat is the immunosuppressed patient. This could be a patient undergoing treatment for an autoimmune disease, receiving cancer treatment, suffering from HIV infection or any number of rare conditions that affect the immune system. Immunosuppression during cancer treatment is usually temporary, the greatest challenge being the resulting hypo salivation (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013). Patients with recurring oral candidiasis due to HIV infection should always be treated in collaboration with their physician. The prophylactic use of antifungal medicine in these patients is sometimes necessary, but can be problematic as it can lead to resistant organisms (Rueping, *et al.*, 2009).

Topical anti-fungal therapy.

The topical agents exist as oral suspensions, pastilles, creams, and tablets. In order for the medicine to have optimal effect, the patient should not rinse their mouth, eat or drink for at least one hour after use (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013). They have few adverse effects in comparison to systemic treatment, and can be used in combination with systemic treatment as it lessens the dose and duration (Akpan and Morgan. 2002).

There is large variety of these medications world-wide of which:

- Nystatin: is widely used and comes in many different formulations, usually liquid suspensions, creams and pastilles, and its efficacy is largely dependent on contact with the oral mucosa or fungal cells (Muzyka, 2005). also is a polyene antifungal agent, and it works by binding to

Ergosterol in fungal cell membranes (Laudenbach and Epstein. 2009).

- Clotrimazole: is an alternative to nystatin that is especially useful in angular cheilitis, due to its effect on both Candida and Staphylococci. (Muzyka, 2005).

In Norway it is available as a cream. It rarely causes adverse effects when applied topically, but nausea, vomiting and local skin irritation may occur (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009).

- Miconazole: is a broad spectrum anti-fungal agent that can be used both topically and systemically, though its systemic use has been stopped as there are fewer toxic alternatives

(Samaranayake, et al., 2009). It is an azole drug, and it has antifungal and antibacterial properties. It has several mechanisms, one of which is inhibition of ergosterol synthesis (Laudenbach and Epstein. 2009).

Systemic anti-fungal therapy.

is preferred in severely immunocompromised patients, and the treatment is usually led by a physician. Fluconazole is the preferred agent (Lalla, *et al.*, 2013). Fluconazole is absorbed well in the gastrointestinal tract and can be taken orally with good effect (Akpan and Morgan. 2002). It has some side effects, like nausea, headache, gastrointestinal discomfort and abdominal discomfort, but these are usually mild (Samaranayake, *et al.*, 2009).

Like miconazole, fluconazole disrupts the ergosterol synthesis in the fungal cell, causing the leakage in the cell membrane and cell death (Akpan and Morgan. 2002).

Conclusion

The candidiasis is of various types affecting different regions in and around the oral cavity. They are usually asymptomatic and rarely produce any problem to the patients, and hence, often missed during routine clinical examination. Also, oral Candidiasis is condition which arises due to some predisposing factors like compromised immune system function and generalized patient debilitation. *Candida albicans* that cause the disease is usually present in oral cavity in an inactive form. In most of cases the disease is often unnoticed and only proper oral examination by the dentist can diagnose it. Furthermore, it should be noted that every white lesion in the oral cavity is not due to the candidal infection.

Obtaining a thorough history and identifying the underlying cause are the first step toward successful management. The treating practitioner should have a complete knowledge about actions and side effects of anti-fungal used for treatment. Although, after the proper laboratory investigation the disease can be confirmed. Diagnosis of oral Candidiasis can be done by microscopic examination and /or biopsy. The disease can be easily controlled by administration topical or systemic antifungal agents. Prognosis of oral Candidiasis is good.

References

1. Aiello. (1977). Systemic Mycoses in modern medicine, *microbiol Immunol.* 32-6.
2. Akpan A, Morgan R. (2002). Oral candidiasis. *Postgraduate Medical Journal.* 78(922):455-9.
3. Arendorf TM, Walker DM. (1987). Denture stomatitis: a review. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation.*; 14(3):217-27.
4. Arendorf TM, Walker DM, (1980). The prevalence and intra-oral distribution of *Candida albicans* in man. *Archives of Oral Biology.* 1980; 25(1):1-10.
5. Ashman RB, Farah CS. (2005). Oral candidiasis: clinical manifestations and cellular adaptive host responses, in *Fungal Immunology*, eds Fidel P. L., Huffnagle G. B., editors. New York, NY: Springer; 59-83.
6. Avcu N, Kanli A. (2003). The prevalence of tongue lesions in 5150 Turkish dental outpatients. *Oral Diseases.*; 9(4):188-195.
7. Behzadi P, Behzadi E. Signoreto C, Burlacchini G, Faccioni F, Zanderigo M, Bozzola N, Canepari P. (2009). Support for the role of *Candida* spp. in extensive caries lesions of children. *The new microbiological.* 2009; 32(1):101.

8. C. L. Taschdjian, J. J. Burchall, and P. J. Kozinn, (1960). "Rapid identification of *Candida albicans* by filamentation on serum and serum substitutes," *A. M. A. Journal of Diseases of Children*, vol. 99, pp. 212–215, 1960.
9. Cannon R, Holmes A, Mason A, Monk B. (1995). Oral *Candida*: clearance, colonization, or candidiasis? *Journal of dental research*. 1995; 74(5):1152-61.3.
10. Cherrick HH. (1998). The mouth and oropharynx. In: "Surgical Pathology" volume 1, 2nd edition, JB Lippincott Company; Philadelphia, USA, 1. Children, vol. 99, pp. 212–215, 1960.
11. Coronado-Castellote L, Jimenez-Soriano Y. (2013). Clinical and microbiological diagnosis of oral candidiasis. *Journal of clinical and experimental dentistry*. ;5(5): e279e86.
12. Dos Santos CM, Hilgert JB, Padilha DM, Hugo FN. (2009). Denture stomatitis and its risk indicators in south Brazilian older adults. *Gerodontology*.; 27(2):134- 40.
13. Dujon B, Sherman D, Fischer G, Durren P, Casaregola S, Lafontaine I, et al. (2004). Genome evolution in yeasts. *Nature*: 430:35-44: PMID:15229592: [http:// dx.doi. org/10.1038/nature 02579](http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature02579).
14. Dupont B, Graybill JR, Armstrong D, Laroche R, Touzé JE, Wheat LJ. (1992). Fungal infections in AIDS patients. *Journal of Medical and Veterinary Mycology*.; 30(1):19-28.
15. E.R. Ballou, G.M. Avelar, D. Schildren's, J. Mackie, J.M. Bin, J. Wagener, S.L. K astora, M.D. Panea, S. E Hardisob, L.A. walker. (2016). Lactate signaling regulates fungal B₁-glucan masking and immune evasion *Nat. Microbiol* ,2,16238.
16. Eckert, L.O.; Lentz, & G.M. (2012). In *Comprehensive Gynecology*; Lentz, G.M.; Lobo, R.A.; Gershenson, D.M.; Katz, V.L., Ed.; 6th ed.; Mosby Elsevier: Philadelphia,
17. Emami E, Kabawat M, Rompre PH, Feine JS. (2014). Linking evidence to treatment for denture stomatitis: A meta- analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of Dentistry*.; 42(2):99-106.
18. Emmons C W, Binford C H, Utz J P, Known-Chung KJ. (1977). *Medical Mycology 3rd ed.* Philadelphia: Lea and Febiger.
19. Epstein JB, (1990). Antifungal therapy in oropharyngeal mycotic Infections. *Oral Surgery Oral Medicine Oral Pathology Oral Radiology*. ,69(1):32-41.
20. Farah CS, Lynch N, McCullough MJ. (2010). Oral fungal infections: an update for the general practitioner. *Australian Dental Journal*.; 55(1):48-54.
21. Fraser VJ, Jones M, Dunkel J, Storfer S, Medoff G, Dunagan WC. (1992). Candidemia in a tertiary care hospital: Epidemiology, risk factors, and predictors of mortality. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 1992; 15(3):414-21.
22. genome sequence of *Candida albicans*," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* Giannini PJ, Shetty KV. (2011). Diagnosis and management of oral candidiasis. *Otolaryngologic clinics of North America*. ;44(1):231-40, vii.
23. Greenspan, D.; John, S.G. (1996). HIV-related oral disease. *Lancet*, 348, 729-734.
24. Guida RA. (1988). Candidiasis of the Oropharynx and Oesophagus. *Ear, Nose and Throat Journal*, 67(11):832, 834-6, 838-840.
25. H.M. Scanela, B. Cardoso, L.H. Vitali, H.C. Coelho, R. Martinez, M.E. D S. Ferreir. (2018). Prevalence, Virulence factor and anti-fungal susceptibility of *Candida* spp., isolated from blood stream infections in a tertiary care hospital in Brazil. *Mycoses* ,61,11_21

26. H.R.conti. A.R. Huppler, N. whibley, & S.L. Gaffen. (2014). Animal models for candidiasis. *curr. protoc. IM* 105,19.6.1_19.6.17.
27. Holmstrup P, Besserman M. (1983). Clinical, therapeutic, and pathogenic aspects of chronic oral multifocal candidiasis. *Oral Surgery Oral Medicine Oral Pathology Oral Radiology*; 56(4):388-395.
28. Iatta R, Napoli C, Borghi E, Montagna MT. (2009). Rare mycoses of the oral cavity: A literature epidemiologic review. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*; 108:647-55.
29. J. Kim, P. Sudbery. (2011). *Candida albicans*, a major human fungal pathogen. *J. Microbiol*, 49,171.
30. J. Savilainen, K. Lammintausta, K. Kalimo, M. Viander. (1993). *Candida albicans* and atopic dermatitis *Clin.Exp. Allergy* 23,332_339.
31. Kaur R, Domergne R, Zupancic ML, Cormack BP, (2005). A Yeast by any other name: *Candida glabrata* and it's interaction with the host. *Curr opin microbiol* ;378-84; PMID:155996895
32. Lalla RV, Patton LL, Dongari-Bagtzoglou A. (2013). Oral candidiasis: pathogenesis, clinical presentation, diagnosis and treatments strategies. *Journal of. The California Dental Association.* ;41(4):263-8.
33. Lamey PJ, Lewis MA. (1989). Oral medicine in practice: angular cheilitis. *British Dental Journal.*; 167(1):15-8.
34. Laudenschlager JM, Epstein JB. (2009). Treatment strategies for oropharyngeal candidiasis. *Expert opinion on. Pharmacotherapy.* 10(9):1413-21.
35. Li, F.Q.; Ma, C.F.; Shi, L.N.; Lu, J.F.; Wang, Y.; Huang, M.; Kong, Q.Q. (2013). Diagnostic value of immunoglobulin G antibodies against *Candida* enolase and fructosebiphosphate aldolase for candidemia. *BMC Infect. Dis.*, 13, 253.
36. Lucas VS. (1993). Association of psychotropic. drugs, prevalence of denture related stomatitis and oral candidosis. *Community Dentistry and Oral Epidemiology.* 1993; 21(5):313-6.
37. M. L. Anderson and F. C. Odds, "Adherence of *Candida Albicans* to vaginal epithelia: significance of morphological Form and effect of ketoconazole," *Mykosen*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 531–540, 1985.
38. M. L. Anderson and F. C. Odds, "Adherence of *Candida Albicans* to vaginal epithelia: significance of morphological Form and effect of ketoconazole," *Mykosen*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 531–540, 1985.
39. M.A. pfuller, D. J Diekema. (2007). Epidemiology invasive candidiasis. A persistent public health problem, *Virulence.* 2 ,119_128.
40. M. A. Gordon,. (1958). "Rapid serological differentiation of *Candida albicans* from *Candida stellatoidea*." *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*, vol.31, no.2, pp. 123–125,
41. Marin Zuluaga DJ, Gomez Velandia OC, Rueda Clauijo DM. (2011). Denture-related stomatitis managed with tissue conditioner and hard autopolymerising reline material. *Gerodontology.* ;28(4):258-63.
42. Maristela Barbosa Portela, Daniella Ferraz Cerqueira, Rosangela Maria de Araújo, Gloria Fernanda Castro. (2012). *Candida* spp. In linear gingival erythema lesions in HIV- infected children: reports of six cases. *International Journal of Science Dentistry.*; 1:51-55.
43. McCullough MJ, Savage NW. (2005). Oral candidosis and the therapeutic use of antifungal agents in dentistry. *Australian dental journal.* ;50(4 Suppl 2): S36-9.

44. Mikulska M, Del Bono V, Ratto S, Viscoli C. (2012). "Occurrence, presentation and treatment of candidemia," Expert Review of Clinical Immunology. 2012; 8(8):755- 765.
45. Muzyka BC. (2005). Oral fungal infections. Dental clinics of North America. ;49(1):49- 65, viii
46. Neville BW, Damm DD, Allen CM, Bouquot JE. (2009). Fungal and protozoal diseases. In: Neville, Damm,
47. Allen, Bouquot Oral and maxillofacial pathology. 3 rd ed . Philadelphia: WB Saunder; p. 224-37.
48. Olsen I. (2010). Orale infeksjoner. In: Rollag H, editor. Medisinsk mikrobiologi. 3 ed. p. 697-717.
49. P faller MA, Diekema DJ, (2004). Rare and emerging opportunistic fungal pathogens: concern for resistance beyond Candida albicans and Aspergillus fumigates. J clin Microbiol ,42:4419-31, PMID:15472288.
50. P faller MA, Diekema DJ, (2007). epidemiology of invasive candidiasis: a persistent public Health problem. Clin microbiol Rev: 20:133-63, PMID:17223626.
51. P. miramon, M.C. Lorenz. (2017). A feast for candida metabolic plasticity confers an edge for virulence. PLoS pathog., 13 eLoo_6244.
52. Patil S, Rao SR, Majumdar B, Sukumaran A. (2015). Clinical Appearance of Oral Candida Infection and Therapeutic Strategies. Frontiers in Microbiology. 6:1391.
53. Patton LL, McKaig RG, Eron Jr JJ, Lawrence HP, Strauss RP. (1999). Oral hairy leukoplakia and oral candidiasis as predictors of HIV viral load. Aids. 13(15):2174.
54. Premanathan M, Shakurfow FAA, Ismail AA, Berfad MA, Ebrahim AT, Awaj MM. '(2011). Treatment of Oral Candidiasis (thrush) by Saccharomyces cerevisiae'. International. Journal of Medicine and Medical. Sciences.; 3(3):83-86.
55. Rautemaa R, Ramage G. (2011). Oral candidosis-clinical challenges of a biofilm disease. Critical reviews in microbiology. ;37(4):328-36.
56. Rogers RS, 3rd, Bruce AJ. (2004). The tongue in clinical diagnosis. Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology.; 18(3):254-259.
57. Rueping MJ, Vehreschild JJ, Cornely OA. (2009). Invasive candidiasis and candidemia: from current opinions to future perspectives. Expert opinion on investigational. drugs.;18(6):735-48.
58. S.w. kashem, B.Z. Igyarto, M. Geremi_Nejad, Y. kumamoto, J. Mohammed, E. Harrette, R.A Drummond, Sim Zurawski, G Zurawski, J Berman. (2015). Candida albicans morphology and dendritic cell subsets determine T helper cell differentiation. Immunity. ,24,350_366.
59. Samaranyake LP, Keung Leung W, Jin L. (2009). Oral mucosal fungal infections. Periodontology 2000. ; 49:3959.
60. Santos MA, Tuite MF, (1995). The CUG codon is decoded in vivo asserine and not leucine in Candida albicans. Nucleic acid Res, 23-:1481-6: PMID:7784200: <http://dx.dio.org:10.1093/nar/ 23.9.1481>.
61. Scully, Crispian. (2008). Oral and Maxillofacial Medicine: the basis of diagnosis and treatment, 2nd. edition Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone, 147-149.
62. Shannon M T, Sclaroff A, Colm S J. (1990). Invasive aspergillosis of the maxilla in a patient with acquired immune deficiency syndrome. Ora l Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol; 48:997-9.
63. Silverman S Jr, Luangjarmekorn L, Greenspan D. (1984). Occurrence of oral Candida in irradiated head and. neck cancer patients. Journal of Oral Medicine. 1984;39(4):194-196.

64. Sims C R, Paetznick V L, Rodriguez J R, Chen E, OstroskyZeichner L. (2006). Correlation between microdilution, E-test, and disk diffusion methods for antifungal susceptibility testing of posaconazole against *Candida* spp. *Journal of clinical microbiology*.; 44(6):2105-8.
65. Sitheequ M A, Samaranayake L P. (2003). Chronic hyperplastic candidosis / candidiasis (Candidal Leukoplakia). *CriticalReviews in Oral Biology and Medicine*.; 14(4):253-267.
66. T. Jones, N. A. Federspiel, H. Chibana et al., (2004). "The diploid genome sequence of *Candida albicans*," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, vol. 101, no. 19, pp. 7329– 7334, 2004.
67. Torre-Cisneros J, Lopez OL, Kusne S, Martinez AJ, Starzl TE. (1993). CNS aspergillosis in organ transplantation: A clinicopathological study. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psych*; 56:188-93.
68. Tyldesley WR, Field A, Longman L, (2003). *Tyldesley's Oral medicine*, 5th edition, Oxford: Oxford University Press.; 37, 40, 46, 63-67.
69. Walsh, T.J.; Dixon, & D.M. (1996). In *Baron's Medical Microbiology*; Samuel Baron, Ed.; Galveston (TX): University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston: Galveston, Texas,
70. Winner HI, Hurley R. (1964). *Candida albicans*. Boston:GA, Davies S Little Brown and Co, Raven press.